

Roman Policy towards Samaritans in the Second Century A.D.

by

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Throughout this article single pieces of data from my book of 2024 and some other publications will be brought in as part of a general picture. So will the conclusions of some arguments. Only what is needed to paint the picture will be quoted. Enough will be repeated to keep the presentation easy to follow. The reader can easily look at the arguments in the original places. I disdain the practice of concocting padded lists of publications. There is some new discovery in this article. One important discovery is that Hadrian spent public money on promoting worship in the sacred place, the top of Mt. Gerizim. Another is the evidence that the office of Patriarch kept up till the end of rule by Pagan Rome. There are a few other pieces. In such cases proof will be given as fully as possible, and the circumstances will be described as fully as possible.

The Patriarch

It is known that the Samaritans did well under Roman rule in the second century A.D. before the accession of Commodus in 180 A.D. The evidence is clear, from multiple directions, with both Samaritan and Jewish attestation of different kinds. It is known that Bāba the son of Nātānel, remembered as Bāba Rabba, Bāba the Great, was High Priest from 134 to 174. ² It is not known if he was secular ruler from the start of his officiate, and was appointed by Hadrian, but there is evidence. Although the record has been badly transmitted, one version says he was the youngest of three sons. If this is right, it would mean he was made High Priest against the usual custom of appointing the eldest son, so that he could then be appointed by Rome as secular ruler. There is another piece of evidence that this happened, and this one is more certain, and to my mind conclusive. When he died, he was succeeded by his brother, not his son. This would have restored the line of succession. The detailed account of his administration as secular ruler of Samaria is well known. The borders of Samaria which had been nibbled at by Jews were restored. It is known that he ruled over the whole population of Samaria, which included

¹ **The author has no connection with the State of Israel.**

² The name Nātānel is stressed on the second syllable, with the alef dropped in pronunciation. It can be written as one word or two, but either way the sound [n] starts the third syllable.

Bāba became High Priest in the year 4560 A.M. [Anno Mundi], which started in late March of 134 A.D., and died during the year 4601 A.M., which started in late March of 174 A.D. The calculations can be found in my book of 2024, note 35 pp. 160 – 161, and near the start of my article *Restoring the Traditional Linkage*. The circumstances of the time of his rule are set out in my book on pp. 11 middle to 13 with extensive documentation.

some Jews inside Samaria but on the fringes. All Jews had been removed to the fringes for the sake of public order. He had authority over some major Samaritan communities outside Samaria in Palestine and southern Phoenicia.³ He had the title of Patriarchos. As far as I have been able to ascertain, this title was unique. If so, it would have been invented to describe his unique status as ruler of a territory and every category of its inhabitants, as well as ruler of some communities outside the territory, as well as High Priest of all Samaritans everywhere, as Tetrarch and a new kind of Ethnarch and High Priest. This was a step beyond the status of the Hasmonaeans under Roman rule, and a new title would have had to be made up.⁴ It is not known if Patriarch and High Priest were his only titles. It can now be shown that the Samaritans were favoured in another way by Hadrian, who put up a complex of buildings on top of Mt. Gerizim, the only conceivable purpose of which would have been to enable pilgrimage and study. It was his practice to do this kind of promotion and benefaction of local religion as well as Roman religion throughout the empire. Sometimes the expenditure was considerable, but this time he went a bit further than usual.

One piece of information about dating that I overlooked in my book of 2024 and my article *Restoring the Traditional Linkage* needs to be considered here, because it is relevant to determining the date of Bāba Rabba. In the interpolation in the Arabic Joshua book it says Hadrian died 4,513 years and seven months from Creation. It says he reigned for 21 years. The length of his reign is correct. In the corresponding version of this long pericope of fictionalised history interpolated into the work of A.F. there is no date, and the length of reign is given as 41 years. It can be shown that there were two different changes both aimed at putting Hadrian's

³ These last two facts render attempts to make him a resistance leader in times of oppression by Rome totally unscientific as well as severely irrational. The same can be said of any attempts to date him without using the datum of the known date of his death and the datum of the length of his officiate. However, very much written on Samaritans is unscientific and a fair bit is irrational. We might think of the unscientific assertion that Bāba, which means “the gate” in the Aramaic of the Babylonian Talmud, means the same in Palestinian Aramaic, which goes with irrational unfounded invention by Crown and Pummer of an **unattested** Babylonian concept of supernatural gatekeepers (not gates) and their invention that the Samaritans copied the Babylonians in this unattested belief. Florentin knows better, but repeated the invention. The rule is that nothing said by one member of the club can ever be contradicted by another member, even if he knows it's wrong. The front of collective omniscience must be maintained. Or we might think of Bowman's explanation of the name Dustān as a Hebrew word with a **Persian** plural ending. Or his belief that the Kitāb at-Ṭubākh says fish must have feathers to be kosher. No, I'm not making this up. See my book *Principles of Samaritan Halachah* p. 13. Or Crown and Stenhouse's belief that one category of Dositheans venerated water in some incomprehensible way. Ignorance of Hebrew and Aramaic is standard. Adler and Séligsohn thought the name Dustān was actually darastān. They had to go against the textual evidence, but that didn't worry them. They thought the name was from the Hebrew verb dāras, which means to press down with any part of the body or the whole body, not necessarily with the feet, but their command of Hebrew was weak, and so was their thinking. They mistakenly thought the word meant treading. They thought treading was the same as walking, and then thought walking must mean the same as being acquainted with other people (I can't follow this part at all), and being acquainted with other people was the same as being a member of an organisation. Bowman and Pummer copied this mess. There are dictionaries, though dictionaries still won't remedy being unable to think rationally.

⁴ The title is attested thoroughly mangled to fit the Samaritan Aramaic sound-system. The Jewish scribes were puzzled by the prosthetic vowel at the start. The pronunciation seems to have been aftērīka. (There is no sheva sound [ə] in Samaritan Aramaic). If so, the stress would be on the third syllable.

arrival in Palestine in the time of the wrong High Priest. It was shown in my book that according to the system known to A.F. the year 4600 A.M. ended in late March of 174 A.D., or in other words, the year 4601 A.M., during which Bāba died, started in late March of 174 A.D. The year 4561 A.M., during which he started officiating, started in late March of 134 A.D. Hadrian died in July of 138 A.D. This would be during 4565 A.M., or 4,564 complete years from Creation, if calculated from that date. The version of this piece of fictionalised history interpolated into the Arabic Joshua book does not put Hadrian in the time of a named High Priest. At the end of the long pericope it says he died 4,513 years and seven months from Creation. The version interpolated into the work of A.F. puts him in the time of the High Priest Iqbon at 113:3 -- 5. But in another place, at 118:5, in a passage not from any fictionalised history it says he came in the time of the High Priest Lībi. In that place the officiates of three High Priests are listed. Iqbon 30 years; Fīnāas 40 years; Lībi 25 years. The figure for the date of the death of Hadrian in the version of the fictionalised history in the Arabic Joshua book has been pushed back by 51 years to fit the new fictionalised history which puts his arrival in Palestine in the time of Iqbon. The figure of seven months is revealing. Hadrian died on the 10th of July. However, seven months from late March is late October. If we work from a new year on the first of January, as in the Roman calendar, Hadrian did die in the seventh month, though not after seven whole months. It seems that a date according to the Roman calendar has been converted, but not quite exactly. Afterwards the figure for the year has been lowered by 51 years to fit the fiction that he arrived in Palestine in the time of Iqbon. Actually, the alteration could have been meant to be exactly fifty years. If the conversion to years of Creation was so crude as to count the months starting at the first of January, and count a part month in the total, in Roman fashion, then the conversion of years will likely be wrong by one year. This is a common mistake when converting years between two different calendars with different starting dates for the year. *The conclusion is that the figures for conversion of years of Creation to years A.D. and B.C. worked out in my book of 2024 and my article correspond to the figures behind the pericope about Hadrian as it left the hand of A.F. Bāba officiated from 134 / 135 to 174 / 175 A.D.*

The benefaction by Hadrian

The long pericope about Hadrian in all extant manuscripts of the work of Abu 'l-Fateḥ [hereinafter A.F.] ⁵ is a replacement of the original. A variant form is part of a set of additions to the Arabic Joshua book. (This pericope is only in one manuscript of the Arabic Joshua book, the one used by Juynboll. All the others have the long pericope about the High Priest's daughter). About seven pericopes of the book by A.F. have been replaced. In nearly every case there is an equivalent in slightly different form attached to the Arabic Joshua book. The evidence is given in my article *Samaritan History, Fiction, and Bad Fantasy*. All the replacements are bad, but some are less bad than others, and this is one of them. If the two forms are used together a lot of the original wording can be recovered. I went a long way with doing this in my book of 2024, on pp. 16 to 19, but missed a piece of highly important information.

In this case Stenhouse's translation of A.F. is accurate enough. Crane's translation of the Arabic Joshua book is sound in this place. For the reader's convenience, I will quote enough for the argument to be followed easily without having either translation to hand. The

⁵ The transcription Abu 'l-Fateḥ, which shows the actual pronunciation, is used for the convenience of readers not knowing Arabic.

interpretations by Bargès and Montgomery and others won't be quoted because they show careless or insensitive reading and would only be a hindrance. Everyone forgot the mountain had two peaks. Bull went as far as thinking the Samaritan sanctuary was on the lower peak in Hadrian's time, without explaining how it could have been on the higher peak before then and after then. He never explained how he thought the Samaritans had come to move their sacred place. A lot of people copied him. Everyone got mixed up between the Samaritan sanctuary and the Pagan temple. Bargès thought the Pagan temple was at the foot of the mountain. I can't imagine how he found that in the text. No-one looked at the representations on coins properly, which show two sacred places on two peaks. Just bear in mind that there are two peaks. The lower one is to the north of the higher one. The lower one overlooks Nablus or Neapolis. The lower one is profane, the higher is sacred. Samaritans reserve the name Mt. Gerizim for the sacred peak and the half-sacred slopes up to it, or just the sacred peak. They call the lower peak the ridge next to Nablus. There is an example of this usage here in the version in the Arabic Joshua book. They would not have been offended by a Pagan temple on the lower peak.

Here is the important part as worded in the interpolation in the extant manuscripts of the work of A.F. I have not copied Stenhouse's translation because the style is not good.

"He [Hadrian] built an enormous temple and called it < sfys > [< sfrs >, sefres, Serapis]".

Here it is as in the addition to the Arabic Joshua book. I depart slightly from Crane's translation for the sake of precision.

"He built a town (or village) on Mt. Gerizim, and called it < sqrs > [< sfrs >] after his father".

But a little bit further on it says this.

"..... the dome he had built on the ridge of the mountain that is next to Neapolis".

Some notes. The wording in the interpolation in A.F. shows it is the Pagan temple that is called Sefres, not the town. A narrative further on in this version makes this certain. The same narrative makes it clear that the Pagan temple was not on what is called Mt. Gerizim by the Samaritans, but the lower peak next to Neapolis. There is some confusion in this version with defilement of Mt. Gerizim under Christian rule and an attack on a church building on the sacred peak by Samaritans because of it, but it is easy to sort out what is what. The full explanation is in my book. In the form in the Arabic Joshua book it can be seen that the first statement of the building of the Pagan temple has been cut out. In that version, there has been bad abridgment due to not reading properly and not seeing that two peaks are mentioned in the story and a village for Samaritan use was put up on the sacred one and Pagan temple on the profane one. Originally there would have been a statement of the building of the town on Mt. Gerizim, that is, the sacred peak, then a statement of the building of the Pagan temple, then the name of the Pagan temple. The words saying Hadrian named the building after his father are a bad guess by the interpolator, who had never heard of Serapis. The reconstruction of the name Serapis is simple and compelling. Details are in my book on p. 19. It says further on in the version interpolated in the work of A.F. that the temple of Serapis was guarded by Samaritans. This trust and conferring of prestigious office is another piece of evidence that they were favoured by the Romans. It also shows they were allowed to bear arms. It says in the version in the Arabic Joshua book that there were Samaritan troops and Hadrian was gracious to them.

Munificence towards sacred places is typical of what Hadrian did. They did not have to be Roman. It was part of his policy of promoting culture in all parts of the empire. This was partly for general benefit, but partly also to help make the parts more definitely parts of a whole, with the people in the different parts wanting to be in the empire. See Dio Cassius, chapter LXIX. Arnold Toynbee has explained how this kind of thing works. In this case, he went further than usual. The surviving sources tell us he had good reason to reward the Samaritans. Although the story about the help he got from two Samaritan brothers improbably called Ephraim and Menasseh is obviously fiction, vague memory of him being supported by the Samaritans in ending the insurrection of a formidable Jewish party survives. He never needed help in taking Jerusalem because it was never held by the insurrectionists. He seems to have had general support from the general Samaritan population, as well as military support. The story in the version of this interpolation in the work of A.F. about Samaritans attacking his temple is from the time of Christian rule when there was a church on the sacred peak. I suppose this is one of the reasons for the general confusion. A little bit of source criticism and editorial criticism --- otherwise called reading carefully --- would have prevented this. There is a detailed examination in my book. If this story about circumstances centuries later is seen for what it is, then what is left is a coherent account of Hadrian rewarding the Samaritans for their support, and showing his trust by making Samaritans the guards of the Pagan temple.

Juynboll says Dio Cassius says at XV:9 that Hadrian put up a temple of Zeus Hypsistos on Mt Gerizim. The reference is a phantom. The information that Hadrian put a temple of the Pagan Zeus up on the profane lower peak has been mixed up by him with the information from Marinos that the Samaritan sanctuary on the sacred higher peak was dedicated to Zeus Hypsistos. The chapter number is a mistake for the mention of the temple of Jupiter put up by Hadrian in Jerusalem in ch. XIV of the entry on Hadrian in the *Historia Augusta*. It has been imagined that the temple of Zeus Hypsistos was Pagan, because of preconceptions and not reading properly. The title Zeus Hypsistos was used by Pagans, but in this case the meaning was different. Argument for the compatibility of the epithet with the religion of Israel is in my book, pp. 12 to 13. The reference to Dio Cassius has been copied by author after author. I have to admit I did it myself in an earlier version of my book without noticing that the reference to ch. XV of the work of Dio Cassius is impossible on the face of it, since Hadrian is in ch. LXIX. This was a useful lesson in method. Never believe anything without looking. Kippenberg is to be credited with first seeing the reference is wrong.

I propose that Hadrian put up buildings connected with the sanctuary. This would have been accommodation for the High Priest and other Priests, accommodation for a lot of people on the three pilgrim festivals and smaller numbers throughout the year, synagogues for a lot of people at the same times, buildings for teaching and study, storehouses, stables and cowsheds, and so on. A town would naturally grow up round this, as it did in times before.

It is not surprising that the Samaritans supported the Romans during the insurrection. They benefited from Roman rule. They had home rule in Samaria and were protected from Jews. Harassment or oppression or murderous attack had been a danger to Samaritans since the time of Saul. (Anachronism in terminology is convenient for simplicity in expression). Samaritans are attacked by Lubavitch and some other Ultra-Orthodox taxi-drivers to this very day. Besides this, the insurrection was senseless. Dio Cassius gives one reason and the author of the *Historia Augusta* gives another, but neither works. Actions taken after the end of the insurrection have been thought to be the cause of it, because neither historian can see any reason

for it. The Rabbinic accounts don't give any reason. Hugo Mantel, to my mind convincingly, concludes that they had nothing to complain about but did not want to be ruled by Romans. When the insurrection was over, there was no repression of Jewish religion. It was only three years later that Antoninus Pius became emperor, and he is spoken of highly favourably in the Rabbinic accounts. It was at this time that work started on the oldest midrashim. It was under Pagan Roman rule that the Mishnah and Tosefta, the oldest midrashim, the Palestinian Talmud, and other foundational works were composed. Work on the Palestinian Talmud stopped literally in mid paragraph as soon as the Christian Church got power over the government. Magen and others say hundreds of thousands of Jews were systematically driven out of Palestine after the two revolts ending in 70 A.D. and 135 A.D. They know better. This story is a piece of Christian propaganda meant to show how the Jews were divinely punished. In modern times a lot of Jews believe this bit of Christian theology. A lot of Jews that are historians promote it dishonestly. Magen is only one example. Their propaganda is expressed in the words of the Israel national anthem, which says all Jews were driven out of Palestine two thousand years ago.

Steps towards home rule in the first century

It is not known whether Bāba was the first Patriarch. There were new circumstances at the time of his appointment. There were other cases of Rome recognising vassal kings or rulers with lower titles and having a hand in their appointment. In some cases the king or ruler was also High Priest. What was unique was that Bāba was both Ethnarch or Tetrarch, and Exilarch. He ruled Samaria, restored to its proper borders, and at the same time had some kind of authority over Samaritans in some big communities outside Samaria. There are signs of steps towards self-government in Samaria in the first century, so creation of the office of Patriarch was not such a big step as might be thought. There isn't much, but it is illuminating.

For a start, it is known that there was a Samaritan Senate no later than 36 A.D. See my book of 2024, p. 95. It was subordinate to the Roman Governor, but it could make a legal complaint against the Governor. In my book, I expressed strong doubt as to whether the massacre was ordered by Pilate and whether the complaint was against him. For the present purpose, the question does not matter.

Then there is the state visit of a Samaritan dignitary to Rome in the time of Claudius. See my book, p. 48. It is certain that Justin is telling the truth when he says this happened because he is so annoyed by it. It is certain that it was a state visit because Justin says he addressed the Senate, and a statue was put up in his honour. It doesn't matter whether a statue really was put up, or whether Justin or his informant misread an inscription dedicating the statue to the Sabine god Semo Sanco. What matters is that Justin believed that could have happened. It is certain that he thinks he is telling a fact because he is so annoyed. It is not certain that the dignitary's name was Simon. If Justin or an informant misread a dedication to Semo Sanco, he would have jumped to the conclusion that this was the Simon vilified by him.

Administration of Samaria was separated from administration of other parts of Palestine after the end of Pilate's term as Governor in March of 37 A.D. Here is the evidence. Tacitus contradicts Josephus on whether Samaria was governed separately from the Galilee before 52 A.D. (Tacitus, *Annals* XII.54. Josephus, *War*, II:247; *Antiquities* XX:137). Tacitus says there was a different administrator in the two places. Josephus says it was the same person. I think it would be better to say this is what is assumed by him. Loss of detail can happen. There is no probable mechanism for the version known to Josephus to change to the version

known to Tacitus. The person administering the Galilee administered Judaea, according to Josephus. Modern historians have difficulty getting their heads round an arrangement with one person administering the Galilee and Judaea and someone else administering Samaria. They can't see the rationale and make far-fetched proposals about changing what is recorded. It's obvious. One person administered two areas inhabited by Jews. Another person administered Samaria, in between the two Jewish areas. It can be seen how memory of this arrangement could be lost. Modern historians carry on about this question without **sensitivity**. Being a historian is not just a matter of collecting data. You have to think about how people were affected. In the same way there is unnecessary guessing about what was done from 52 A.D. onwards. If the information available is read with sensitivity to how people were affected, it is obvious that one person administered the Galilee and Samaria, and someone else administered Samaria. Samaritans and Galilean Jews could get on with each other and are known to have been in contact. Judaeans could not get on with anyone. The situation was that Judaeans were kept away from Samaritans before and after 52 A.D. If you read with sensitivity to how people were affected and would have felt, both arrangements, the one up to 52 A.D. and the other after then, separated the job of governing the Samaritans from Judaeans. The second arrangement also separated the job of governing Judaeans from the job of governing everyone else. Different skills and experience were needed.

The conclusion is that after the end of Pilate's term in early 37 A.D. Judaeans were treated carefully. The Samaritans did not have self-rule but it was closer than before. Remember the Samaritan Senate was there. It has been seen that the legal system was responsive and could be used by them. It is possible that the Samaritans had more autonomy after the end of the Jewish revolt, to help guard against new unrest. All that is known about administration is that Samaria was always administered separately from Judaea.

The Apóphasis Megálē attributed to someone called Simon

When Justin of Neapolis was writing, Samaria was ruled by Bāba and some big Samaritan communities outside Samaria were under his authority. In the light of this knowledge, we can try to decode what he says about Samaritan religion at the time. In my book of 2024, pp. 43 middle to 50 and specially pp. 48 to 50, there is detailed study and analysis of Justin's long efforts to get influence in the Roman Senate, doubtless by siding with anyone that wanted something compatible with what he wanted. There is no need to repeat it here.

He says nearly all Samaritans are followers of the teachings of Simon. He might be exaggerating, but he expected to be believed. He complains that this is not only in Samaria, and mentions successful preaching by Menander in Antioch. Simon is not another name for Dositheos. For one thing, the dates don't quite fit. For another, it is unlikely that anyone would have been known by two different names if neither was symbolic. What seems conclusive is that Justin says nearly all Samaritans are followers of Simon. If this was not true he would have been contradicted sooner or later. If the statement is true, then a lot of members of both parties, the Dositheans and the Sebuaeans, must have used the book ascribed to someone by this name. In ch. VIII of the book of Acts, Simon does not represent Dositheos. He is a personification of Samaritan religion. For the device to work, he has to be an embodiment of the religion as well, that is to say, there must have been a Samaritan teacher called Simon. When Justin was scheming, there were teachers in the tradition of this Simon. It seems inevitable to conclude that they used the book ascribed to Simon. The ascription was more likely authentic than not.

The question comes down to what was in the book. When Justin was vilifying Samaritans in the guise of an invented unique kind of gnostic, using the term loosely, Bāba was ruling. The balance of probability is that Marqe and Ninna and ʿamram Dāre wrote at this time, or perhaps just before. We have the sober official pamphlet known to Kelsos addressing former Samaritans that had been inveigled by Christianity. The book ascribed to Simon sits squarely within the religion of Israel. The concept of the energy or impetus or nourishment behind Creation, symbolised by fire, which is prominent in the book ascribed to Simon, is also in the Torah and the hymns by Marqe. This was not a time when most Samaritans fitted Justin's picture. (They never did). For the fiction to work, it had to be a caricature, not original.

Justin says Menander was teaching that followers of Simon would not die. He pretends that means they wouldn't die of old age. He defeats himself in his fervour. No-one could ever have taught that. He says the teaching is rubbish, but thought the same claim by Christianity to be reasonable and true. The teaching is another facet of the concept of shedding of dross and becoming more like the creative fire, which is expressed in the part of the book that survives. The glossator to the surviving fragment is right in quoting John the Baptist. John spoke of the wrath to come. This was similar to what Menander meant by death. John attacked people that wanted a formula that exempted them from the working of the creative fire while they continued deliberately unregenerate. For the followers of Simon, the process was easy. This concept was expressed from a different angle by the Ebionites. See p. 65 of my book.

Now we can see part of the reason that Samaritan religion was a threat to Christianity. Christianity *as actually preached* says believe in Jesus and you'll be all right. The essence of it is the same as what John denounced. Christianity obscured the meaning by having John seem to attack Sadducees and Pharisees. When the change was made, Sadducees and Pharisees were just names to the Christian church. No-one knew what they were but they sounded bad. The teaching in the book ascribed to Simon has not got the fallacy of thinking that human effort is enough on its own. The book speaks of coming to be more and more like the fire or like the Great Power and the Boundless Power. The Ebionites spoke of a lifting up from above, but this has to be deserved by work and goodwill. The weakness of much of Pagan ethics is not there. At the same time the weakness of Christianity, relying on a magic formula, is not there either.

Pagan Rome and Christian Rome

Justin tried to get the Roman Senate to wipe out Samaritan religion. This sounds unbelievable but he said so himself in the last two paragraphs of his Second Apology. He makes it clear that he wants this done for the convenience of Christianity by putting the explicit request at the end of a promotion of Christians and Christianity. This pamphlet is couched as a petition to the Senate as a whole, but if Justin wanted it to have any effect, he would have had to connive with a faction of senators. If he thought Romans would care about the convenience of the Christian Church he was deluding himself. Still, there might have been some kind of oppression in the time of Commodus. If this really happened, pressure would have had to come from the Senate, because Commodus was not interested in anything outside the city of Rome, and not much interested in attending to matters of state. When writing my book of 2024, I believed the accounts of persecution in the work of A.F. as we have it. I believed these seven or so pericopes to be from the hand of A.F. Like everyone else, I was wrong. I did not see the significance of the correspondence to one of the seven or so episodes of fictionalised history and pure fiction in the additions to the Arabic Joshua book. Neither did I see the significance of the accounts of

persecution as a prelude to the fictitious account of the birth of Bāba at the wrong time and as son of the wrong Nātānel. Or the significance of the total contradiction between the record of careful **undisturbed** administration in Samaria and over **some other Samaritan communities outside Samaria** taken from the Tūlāda, on one hand, and his continual skirmishing with Roman forces, on the other hand. Worst of all, I did not give enough weight to the anomalousness of such a departure from standard Roman policy in regard to local religions, along with how what was described fitted the worst years of Christian Rome in Samaria. In my article *Samaritan History, Fiction, and Bad Fantasy* I pointed out that all the inferior narratives attached at the end of the Arabic Joshua book are in the extant manuscripts of the work of A.F. I argued that in seven or so places a pericope has been replaced by a pericope from a low-grade collection of fictionalised history with some witless fantasy. I now see it was not a collection but a composition in seven or so episodes intended to complete the Arabic Joshua book. What was not complete fantasy was invented using what A.F. wrote supplemented by Jewish records. The chapters from a second try were arrogantly and destructively interpolated into the work of A.F. It was probably at the same time that the date of writing given by A.F. was arrogantly and destructively changed to the date of the selective damage. See my book, note 35 on p. 160.

The record that Septimius Severus offered to make the Samaritan leader his official representative in some way is not the kind of thing that would be made up. It might have been as ruler of Pagans in Samaria or only Neapolis in the name of the Emperor. Whatever the offer was, it was an offer of one kind of authority that Bāba had not had. It entailed the obligation of offering some sacrifices. It might have enabled the granting of special status to Neapolis and benefits to the citizens in how they were taxed. In the fictionalised history the question of tax is misunderstood on purpose and over-dramatised. The legal facts are turned into malicious advice. Four inter-connected pieces of data about administration have been preserved but falsely described. This is useful information about how the falsifier worked. He tried to do the same with the opposition to a new tax under Gordian but could not think of anything and just muddled the narrative and hinted at sinister intent. The record of a state visit of the Samaritan leader to Rome in the time of Philip has been made vague, but the fact can be believed. In the light of this discovery about how the falsifier composed, I think the office of Patriarch might have been vacant under Commodus and restored by Septimius Severus, or it might have been redefined by him.⁶ If so, this would have made it easier for the falsifier to get away with making Bāba son of the wrong Nātānel. The other trick was taking the date of Bāba's death in the Tūlāda to be the date of the start of his activity. Then he dodged questions about the date of his death by saying it was unknown because he never came back from his state visit. This was still not enough, so Hadrian's death was set too early so that Severus would be earlier. He could get away with this because he could say he was altering a Roman record, not a Samaritan one. He set the stage by contradicting A.F. by inserting vilification of Hadrian, leaving confusion in this part. The coins of Neapolis confirm this reconstruction. The Samaritan sanctuary is

⁶ In my book, in footnote 16 on p. 13, I pointed out that the term Tā'ēba occurs twice in the Durrān collection. When writing that note, I agreed with Kippenberg that the collection was from the second century. I was the first to see that there is a mention of Samaritans being forced to set up alien symbols on the sanctuary building. I argued that this mention must be from the time of Commodus. If what happened under Commodus was less severe than in the extant record, then the form of the record would have to be dated to the time of Christian rule. This is not at all certain, however. Commodus often behaved oddly. Even if redating is needed, it remains that the term is much older than the fourteenth century, and my arguments that it was originally a Sebuaean term stand.

consistently put on the coins. It would have been cheaper to only depict the Pagan temple on the lower peak next to the city. The coins from the reign of Philip and Oticilia are as carefully detailed in their representation as the ones from the reign of Antoninus Pius, that is, the time of Bāba Rabba himself. In the light of all this I propose that except for a possible short interruption under Commodus, **the office of Patriarch kept going till the end of Pagan Rome**. *This would explain why Philip is said to have ruled from Constantinople in the fictionalised history. It would explain why the witless stories that are pure fantasy put Bāba in the time of rule from Constantinople, with an active lifetime of at least 130 years from the falsified date of birth. It would explain how the version of the story attached to the Arabic Joshua book about the worthy Roman official Girmon could be irrationally connected with Bāba.*

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